

Work Resilience of Secondary School Teachers in Gerona, Tarlac

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the work resilience skills of secondary school teachers in Gerona, Tarlac and examined their relationship with selected personal and professional profiles. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study involved 218 secondary school teachers from two public schools and one private school. Data were gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire checklist validated by experts in guidance, counseling, and research. Frequency counts, percentage distributions, weighted means, and Pearson contingency coefficient were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that most respondents were female, married, below 30 years old, earned a monthly salary of PHP 20,000-25,000, held a master's degree, had attended school-based in-service trainings, were affiliated with public

schools, and had five years or less of teaching experience. The teachers' work resilience skills were very much manifested across energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation, with energy obtaining the highest mean and focus obtaining the lowest, although still interpreted as very much manifested. Correlation results showed that age and monthly salary were significantly related to all work resilience dimensions, while sex and civil status were not significantly related. Among professional variables, years in service was significantly related to all resilience dimensions, highest educational attainment was significantly related to balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation, and type of school affiliated was significantly related only to focus. The study concludes that teachers generally demonstrate strong resilience, but targeted professional development is needed to strengthen focus, coping responses, and sustained adaptive capacity.

Keywords: *work resilience, secondary school teachers, teacher well-being, stress management, professional development, Gerona Tarlac*

INTRODUCTION

Quality of life in the workplace is a continuing concern in education because teachers perform multiple academic, social, and emotional responsibilities. As learning environments become increasingly complex, teachers are expected not only to master instructional delivery but also to manage challenges involving learners, colleagues, school leaders, parents, and community stakeholders. In such conditions, work resilience becomes essential because it enables teachers to adapt, recover, and remain productive despite stress, pressure, and uncertainty.

Work resilience refers to the capacity to withstand difficult situations, maintain motivation, and bounce back from workplace demands. The World Health Organization (2015) described stress as a major health concern of the 21st century, while the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2012) emphasized that teacher quality is central to improving education standards. For teachers, resilience is therefore not merely a personal strength; it is also a professional capacity that supports instructional effectiveness and learner development.

The study focused on five work resilience dimensions: energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation. These dimensions reflect the teacher's ability to sustain physical and mental strength, maintain equilibrium, concentrate on tasks, build supportive relationships, and adjust to changing work conditions. Previous literature suggests that energy management prevents burnout (Erickson, 2014), focus supports judgment accuracy and problem-solving (Kiken & Shook, 2015), balance reduces strain (Achor, 2016), interaction strengthens social support (Goleman, 2006), and adaptation enables recovery from stressors (Luthans et al., 2006).

In Gerona, Tarlac, secondary school teachers work across both public and private settings where institutional expectations, professional requirements, and learner needs may influence their resilience. Understanding the relationship between teachers' profiles and their resilience skills can guide school administrators and education managers in designing development programs that support teacher well-being and performance. Thus, this study assessed the work resilience skills of secondary school teachers and determined whether their personal and professional profiles were significantly related to the degree of resilience manifested.

Literature Review

Work Resilience and Teacher Well-Being

Research on stress and resilience indicates that work resilience is shaped by attitudes, behaviors, and social supports that can be developed over time. Resilient workers are able to remain motivated in the face of increasing demands, complexity, and change. Coutu (2002) described resilience as involving acceptance of reality, belief in meaning, and the ability to improvise, while Bonanno (2014) emphasized that resilient individuals maintain stable psychological and physical functioning even after disruptive experiences.

Within education, teacher resilience is especially important because teachers serve as front liners in the teaching-learning process. They are required to manage instructional demands while also responding to emotional, behavioral, and administrative concerns. The OECD (2012) identified teacher quality as a key factor in raising educational standards; therefore, strengthening teacher resilience contributes not only to personal well-being but also to school effectiveness.

Dimensions of Work Resilience

Energy enables teachers to sustain effort despite physically and emotionally demanding work. Erickson (2014) suggested that energy management allows employees to reset attention and preserve resilience over time. Balance refers to the ability to maintain stability amid stressful or unexpected situations. Achor (2016) explained that managing cognitive tasks and creating balance in daily routines can reduce strain and support positive functioning.

Focus is the exercise of self-control and concentration while performing tasks. Kiken and Shook (2015) found that focus predicts judgment accuracy and insight-related problem solving, which are important in teaching contexts. Interaction refers to building relationships and social support when confronted with difficult situations. Goleman (2006) emphasized the role of social intelligence in developing positive human relationships. Adaptation, meanwhile, is the capacity to adjust to change and withstand difficult environments, a concept linked with psychological capital and resilience development (Luthans et al., 2006).

Teacher Profiles and Resilience

Personal and professional characteristics may shape the extent to which teachers manifest resilience. Bonanno et al. (2007) found that resilience may be influenced by demographic and contextual factors such as age, education, income, social support, and exposure to stressful life events. In schools, factors such as educational attainment, school affiliation, training exposure, and years in service may also influence the teacher's confidence, coping behavior, and ability to adapt to challenges.

The literature suggests that resilience is not developed in isolation. It is influenced by personal resources and workplace conditions. Thus, examining teachers' profiles together with resilience dimensions provides a practical basis for designing professional development interventions that respond to actual teacher needs.

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. This design was appropriate because the study described the work resilience skills of secondary school teachers and examined the relationship between these skills and selected personal and professional profiles. Descriptive data were used to summarize respondents' characteristics and resilience levels, while correlational analysis determined whether significant relationships existed among the study variables.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Gerona, Tarlac, involving secondary school teachers from Corazon C. Aquino High School, Tagumbao High School, and Gerona Junior College. These schools represented the public and private secondary school settings included in the study.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The respondents were 218 secondary school teachers from two public schools and one private school in Gerona, Tarlac. The participating schools had 137 teachers from Corazon C. Aquino High School, 37 teachers from Tagumbao High School, and 44 teachers from Gerona Junior College. Purposive sampling was used to select schools with a large number of secondary school teachers, while total enumeration was used to include the identified teacher respondents.

Research Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire checklist was used as the primary data-gathering instrument. The first part gathered the personal and professional profiles of the respondents, including age, sex, civil status, monthly salary, highest educational attainment, type of school affiliated, seminars and trainings attended, and years of teaching experience. The second part measured work resilience skills in terms of energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation using a five-point Likert scale.

Validation of the Instrument

The questionnaire was submitted for content validation to five experts in guidance, counseling, and research. Their comments and suggestions were considered in refining the final instrument. The instrument was evaluated and approved by the adviser and critic reader before administration.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher personally administered and retrieved the survey questionnaire from the respondents. Standard procedures were followed in collecting the data, and all responses were treated with confidentiality.

Data Analysis

Frequency counts and percentage distributions were used to describe the respondents' personal and professional profiles. Weighted means were used to determine the degree of manifestation of work resilience skills. Pearson contingency coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the degree of manifestation of work resilience skills at the 0.05 level of significance. Data were encoded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

Ethical Consideration

The study observed voluntary participation and confidentiality of responses. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, and the data gathered were used only for academic and research purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal and Professional Profile of the Respondents

The respondents' profiles indicate that the secondary teacher population in Gerona, Tarlac was generally young, predominantly female, mostly married, and mostly within the PHP 20,000-25,000 salary range. Professionally, many respondents were master's degree graduates, had attended school-based trainings, were affiliated with public schools, and had five years or less of teaching experience. These characteristics provide the context for interpreting their work resilience skills, particularly because age, salary, education, and years in service may shape teachers' coping resources and workplace adjustment.

Table 1. *Personal Profile of the Respondents (n = 218)*

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 30 years old	91	41.70
Age	30 to 39 years old	49	22.50
Age	40 to 49 years old	30	13.80
Age	50 to 59 years old	19	8.70
Age	60 years and above	29	13.30
Sex	Male	92	42.20
Sex	Female	126	57.80
Civil Status	Single	96	44.00
Civil Status	Married	105	48.20
Civil Status	Widow/Widower	17	7.80
Monthly Salary	PHP 20,000 below	24	11.01
Monthly Salary	PHP 20,000 to 25,000	133	61.01
Monthly Salary	PHP 25,001 to 30,000	22	10.09
Monthly Salary	PHP 30,001 to 35,000	27	12.39
Monthly Salary	PHP 35,001 to 40,000	12	5.50

Table 2. *Professional Profile of the Respondents (n = 218)*

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percent
Highest Educational Attainment	Baccalaureate Degree	80	36.70
Highest Educational Attainment	With Master's Degree Units	25	11.57
Highest Educational Attainment	Master's Degree Graduate	91	41.74
Highest Educational Attainment	With Doctor's Degree Units	10	4.59
Highest Educational Attainment	Doctor's Degree Graduate	12	5.50
Trainings/Seminars Attended	School-Based	209	95.87
Trainings/Seminars Attended	District/Division	157	72.02
Trainings/Seminars Attended	Regional	3	1.38
Trainings/Seminars Attended	National	7	3.21
Trainings/Seminars Attended	International	50	22.94
Type of School Affiliated	Public School	174	79.82

Type of School	Private School	44	20.18
Affiliated			
Length of Teaching Experience	5 years and below	105	48.17
Length of Teaching Experience	6 to 15 years	38	17.43
Length of Teaching Experience	16 to 25 years	40	18.35
Length of Teaching Experience	26 years and above	35	16.06

Degree of Manifestation of Work Resilience Skills

The respondents very much manifested all five dimensions of work resilience. Energy obtained the highest weighted mean (4.53), followed by balance (4.45), interaction (4.40), adaptation (4.40), and focus (4.30). The overall mean of 4.41 indicates that the teachers generally possessed strong work resilience skills. Although focus was still very much manifested, it received the lowest mean, suggesting that concentration, response to negative feedback, and sustained self-control during stressful situations may require greater support through professional development activities.

Table 3. *Summary of Work Resilience Skills of Teachers*

Work Resiliency Dimension	Weighted Mean	Description
Energy	4.53	Very Much Manifested
Balance	4.45	Very Much Manifested
Focus	4.30	Very Much Manifested
Interaction	4.40	Very Much Manifested
Adaptation	4.40	Very Much Manifested
Overall Mean	4.41	Very Much Manifested

The high level of energy suggests that teachers were able to maintain physical and mental strength while facing workplace demands. This supports the view that energy management is essential in preventing exhaustion and maintaining productivity (Erickson, 2014). The high results for balance, interaction, and adaptation also indicate that the respondents were able to maintain optimism, develop supportive relationships, and adjust to changing conditions. These findings are consistent with the literature on resilience as a capacity for positive adaptation despite stress and adversity (Bonanno, 2014; Luthar et al., 2010).

Relationship Between Personal Profile and Work Resilience Skills

The correlation results showed that age and monthly salary were significantly related to all work resilience dimensions. In contrast, sex and civil status were not significantly related to any of the resilience dimensions. This indicates that maturity and economic status may be associated with the way teachers manifest energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation, while sex and civil status did not account for significant differences in resilience manifestations.

Table 4. *Relationship Between Personal Profile and Work Resilience Skills*

Dimension	Profile Variable	C-Value	p-value	Interpretation
Energy	Age	0.299*	0.000	Significant
Energy	Salary	0.216*	0.031	Significant
Balance	Age	0.740*	0.000	Significant
Balance	Salary	0.525*	0.000	Significant
Focus	Age	0.663*	0.000	Significant
Focus	Salary	0.358*	0.018	Significant
Interaction	Age	0.574*	0.000	Significant

Interaction	Salary	0.541*	0.000	Significant
Adaptation	Age	0.514*	0.000	Significant
Adaptation	Salary	0.528*	0.000	Significant
All dimensions	Sex	0.019-0.132	0.170-0.784	Not Significant
All dimensions	Civil Status	0.057-0.148	0.161-0.698	Not Significant

The significant relationship between age and work resilience may be explained by differences in life experience, workplace exposure, and coping maturity. Older teachers may have accumulated more strategies for handling stress, while younger teachers may rely on energy and professional motivation. The significant relationship between salary and resilience may also reflect the role of financial stability in reducing stress and supporting work engagement. This interpretation is consistent with Bonanno et al. (2007), who noted that resilience can be influenced by demographic and resource-related factors.

Relationship Between Professional Profile and Work Resilience Skills

Professional profile variables showed more varied relationships with work resilience. Years in service was significantly related to all dimensions, indicating that teaching experience may strengthen resilience across energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation. Highest educational attainment was significantly related to balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation, but not to energy. Type of school affiliated was significantly related only to focus.

Table 5. Relationship Between Professional Profile and Work Resilience Skills

Dimension	Significant Professional Variables	Not Significant Professional Variables
Energy	Years in service ($C = 0.261, p = 0.001$)	Highest educational attainment; Type of school affiliated
Balance	Highest educational attainment ($C = 0.373, p = 0.000$); Years in service ($C = 0.686, p = 0.000$)	Type of school affiliated
Focus	Highest educational attainment ($C = 0.355, p = 0.000$); Type of school affiliated ($C = 0.257, p = 0.000$); Years in service ($C = 0.573, p = 0.000$)	None
Interaction	Highest educational attainment ($C = 0.377, p = 0.000$); Years in service ($C = 0.560, p = 0.000$)	Type of school affiliated
Adaptation	Highest educational attainment ($C = 0.397, p = 0.000$); Years in service ($C = 0.516, p = 0.000$)	Type of school affiliated

The results imply that teaching experience is a consistent factor associated with resilience. Teachers who have spent more years in service may have encountered a wider range of classroom, administrative, and interpersonal challenges, enabling them to develop coping strategies and adaptive responses. The significant relationships involving educational attainment suggest that postgraduate education may help teachers strengthen balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation by exposing them to broader professional knowledge and reflective practice. The significant relationship between school type and focus may reflect differences in workplace structures, expectations, and school cultures between public and private settings.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that secondary school teachers in Gerona, Tarlac generally demonstrated very high work resilience skills across energy, balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation. Among these dimensions, energy was the most strongly manifested, while focus was the least manifested but still remained at a very high level. The findings indicate that teachers possessed strong capacity to sustain effort, maintain balance, relate positively with others, and adapt to work-related challenges.

The study further concludes that selected personal and professional characteristics were significantly associated with work resilience. Age and monthly salary were significantly related to all resilience dimensions, while sex and civil status were not significantly related. Among professional variables, years in service was significantly related to all dimensions, highest educational attainment was related to balance, focus, interaction, and adaptation, and type of school affiliated was related only to focus. These findings suggest that resilience is shaped not only by individual disposition but also by experience, professional growth, and work context.

Recommendation

The Department of Education and school administrators should provide sustained opportunities for teachers to attend professional development programs, particularly those focused on stress management, coping skills, mindfulness, and work resilience. Training opportunities may be expanded beyond school-based activities to include district, division, regional, national, and international seminars so teachers can gain wider exposure to resilience-building practices.

Education managers should design action plans that strengthen positive thinking, emotional regulation, and stress coping mechanisms among teachers. Since focus received the lowest mean among the resilience dimensions, schools should include workshops on concentration, response to negative feedback, reflective practice, and classroom-based stress management in their annual implementation plans.

School leaders should consider mentoring and peer-support systems that connect less experienced teachers with more experienced colleagues. Since years in service was significantly related to all resilience dimensions, structured mentoring may help beginning teachers develop adaptive coping skills, professional confidence, and stronger workplace relationships.

Future researchers may replicate the study in other municipalities or school divisions and may include additional variables such as workload, organizational climate, teacher burnout, administrative support, and mental health indicators to provide a broader understanding of teacher resilience.

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